

JURISPRUDENCE

CONSTITUTIONAL COMPETENCIES OF THE PRESIDENT IN THE REPUBLIC OF KOSOVO IN RELATION TO THE JUSTICE SYSTEM

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Abstract

This scientific paper will analyze the constitutional powers of the President of the Republic of Kosovo with justice system, in terms of appointing and dismissing judges and prosecutors, rejecting proposals from the Kosovo Judicial or Prosecutorial Council for the appointment of judges or prosecutors, the President's power to grant pardons, the latter being elaborated on through statistics on how many convicted persons have been pardoned by several Presidents during their mandates.

The methodology applied consists of the, descriptive method, legal analytical method and comparative method.

From the research it results that the President of the Republic of Kosovo is a representative of the unity of the people and at the same time a guarantor for the democratic functioning of the institutions in the state, including the justice system.

Keywords: Judges, prosecutors, pardon, President, justice system.

1. Introduction

The principle of separation and checks and balances between powers constitutes the foundation on which the constitutional system of the Republic of Kosovo is based. Within the framework of the separation of powers, according to the Constitution, the President of the Republic of Kosovo is attributed with representing the unity of the people, representing the country internally and externally, as well as guaranteeing the democratic functioning of the institutions of the Republic of Kosovo. The justice system is considered an integral part of all constitutions and as such has a place in the Constitution of the Republic of Kosovo. A separate chapter of the constitution includes not only the judiciary, but also the Prosecution and the Bar.

Relations with the judiciary are traditionally permanent relations of the Head of State in any form of regime. Depending on the different systems of government, the powers of the head of state with the judiciary also vary. In Kosovo, Article 84 of the Constitution of the Republic of Kosovo lists presidential powers which can be grouped into three categories: personal, interdependent and ceremonial powers. The paper will address some of the President's own and subordinate constitutional powers in Kosovo, such as the appointment or dismissal of judges and prosecutors, refusal to appoint judges and prosecutors, and the proclamation of individual pardons (Constitution of the Republic of Kosovo, 2008).

2. The appointment and dismissal of judges and prosecutors from the President of the Republic of Kosovo

Courts are constitutional categories. And of

course, when it comes to the organization of the judiciary, both at the constitutional and legal levels, in most democratic countries a collegial body is foreseen, which deals with the appointments, transfers, career, education or qualification, discipline of judges and in some countries, also that of prosecutors. For this purpose, the constitution has conceived the Judicial Council as a completely independent body, which ensures the independence and impartiality of the judicial system (Panda, 2010, p. 88). The Constitution of Kosovo provides for a hybrid system of appointment and dismissal of judges where these powers are divided between the President and the Judicial Council (Morina, 2012, p. 140). It is clearly seen that this competence of the president is a dependent competence, since the appointment of the President of the Supreme Court and other judges depends on the proposal made by the Judicial Council.

In the Republic of Kosovo, the constitution only stipulates the appointment and dismissal of the President of the Supreme Court, while the appointment and dismissal of the Presidents of Basic Courts, supervisory judges, and the President of the Court of Appeal is stipulated by article 7 of the Law on the Judicial Council (Law No. 06/L-055 on Kosovo Judicial Council, 2018). As can be seen, the body and procedure for electing court presidents is the same, only the level of the legal basis for determining their election changes (Bajrami, 2011, p. 318). The Constitution does not specify whether the President may reject the proposals made by the Judicial Council for the appointment or reappointment of judges. However, this issue is regulated by the Law on the Kosovo Judicial Council, which has provided for the right of the President to reject the appointment or reappointment of

a candidate proposed by the Kosovo Judicial Council. Regarding the rejection made, the President is obliged to provide the reasons that influenced making such a decision, which he presents to the Judicial Council based on article 22 (Law No. 06/L-055 on Kosovo Judicial Council, 2018). Through this legal restriction, the president, in addition to the right to appoint, also has the right to reject the proposals made for the first time by the Judicial Council for any candidate.

In addition to the appointment and dismissal of judges, the Constitution of the Republic of Kosovo also regulates the appointment and dismissal of prosecutors. In the case of prosecutors, the appointment procedure is similar to that of judges. Upon the proposal of the Prosecutorial Council, the President appoints and dismisses the Chief State Prosecutor and prosecutors of other levels (Constitution of the Republic of Kosovo, 2008). Therefore, here too a hybrid system of appointment and dismissal of prosecutors is envisaged, where the powers are divided between the Prosecutorial Council and the President. Furthermore, the appointment and dismissal process is regulated by the Law on the Kosovo Prosecutorial Council and the Law on the State Prosecution, the latter with its content regulating the organization, powers and duties of the State Prosecutor and at the same time defining the State Prosecutors throughout the territory of the state and their powers. In this sense, the constitution has determined that the composition of the prosecutorial council as well as the rules for the appointment and dismissal, mandate and organizational structure of the State Prosecutor are determined by law (Hasani, E & Cukalovic I., 2013, p. 551), unlike the judicial system where the above issues are sanctioned by the constitution.

The Law on the Prosecutorial Council regulates the right of the President to reject candidates proposed for prosecutors, similarly to candidates proposed for judges.

Furthermore, Article 7 of the Law on the Judicial Council and the Law on the Prosecutorial Council oblige these two councils to report to the President on their work, which reporting has only an informative character (Law No. 06/L-055 on Kosovo Judicial Council, 2018); (Law No. 06/L-056 on Kosovo Prosecutorial Council, 2019). Through this reporting by these councils, the role that the President of the Republic of Kosovo has in the administration of justice is highlighted.

3. The competence of the President of the Republic of Kosovo to declare individual pardons

Like many constitutions of different countries, the Constitution of the Republic of Kosovo has also guaranteed the President the right to declare a pardon (Constitution of the Republic of Kosovo, 2008). This pardon, based on the constitutional provision, is made by the President of the state by intervening in the acts of the judiciary and avoiding further suffering of the individual who has committed a criminal offense and has been sentenced with a final judgment (Ismaili,

2012, p. 88). A pardon is a right of the president that aims to use an irregular and rare means to reward exceptional behavior and character or to address exceptional humanitarian concerns. A pardon offers the convicted person immediate rehabilitation.

As mentioned above, the Constitution has not limited the pardon. However, Law No. 03/L-101 on Pardon has imposed restrictions, thus defining the categories of persons convicted of certain criminal offenses who are exempt from pardon. This Law on the article 2 defines pardon as “the extraordinary executive power of the President to pardon persons convicted of a criminal offense, releasing them from the punishment determined by the court” (Law No. 03/L-101 on Pardon). As such, it should fall within the executive powers of the President, since the exercise of this power is the sole prerogative of the President and depends on his discretion.

President Hashim Thaqi² from 2016 to 2019 has decreed the pardon of a total of fifty (50) convicted persons (Decree of pardon, “Decree no.: DF-01/2017, Df-02/2017, DF-01-2018, DF-02-2018, DF-03-2018, DF-66/2019, DF-112/2019, DF-148/2019.”).

President Atifete Jahjaga³ on the fourth anniversary of Kosovo’s independence, precisely in 2012, had decreed the pardon of fifteen (15) convicted persons (Decree of pardon, “Decree no.: DF-002-2012”, 2012), in 2013 she had decreed the pardon of four (4) convicted persons (Decree of pardon, “Decree no.: DF-001-2013”, 2013) and in 2014 she decreed the pardon of two (2) convicted persons (Decree of pardon, “Decree no.: DF-001-2014”, 2014). While in 2015 she did not decree the pardon of any convicted person. This finding was given based on the Official Gazette, where in 2015 we did not publish any decree on the pardon of convicted persons, knowing that a copy of the presidential decree on the pardon of convicted persons, in addition to the Ministry of Justice and the persons pardoned by that decree, must be submitted to and published in the Official Gazette of the Republic of Kosovo.

If we compare the number of pardons decreed by President Jahjaga during her five-year mandate with her predecessors, specifically former President Fatmir Sejdiu and Acting President Jakup Krasniqi⁴ and her successor Mr. Hashim Thaqi, it turns out that the total number of pardons is twenty-one, a very small number in relation to the pardons decreed by former President Sejdiu⁵ after the declaration of independence during his two-year mandate in power, where he decreed the pardon of a total of one hundred and twenty-four (124) convicted persons (Decree of pardon “Decree no.: DF-002-2009” & “Decree no.: DF-001-2010”, 2009 & 2010), while in this respect the acting president Jakup Krasniqi leads, who during the time he exercised this function in 2011 had decreed the pardon of one hundred and three (103) convicted persons (Decree of pardon, “Decree no.: DF-001-2011”, 2011). From this it results that President Fatmir Sejdiu, although he had not held a full constitutional mandate, had managed to decree the pardon of an extremely large number of convicts, the same had been done by the acting President Jakup

² He was President during the period 2016-2020.

³ She was President during the period 2011-2016.

⁴ He was Acting President during the period 2010-2011.

⁵ He was President during the period 2008-2010.

Krasniqi who had decreed the pardon of almost the same number of convicts as the former President Sejdiu had decreed for two consecutive years. While President Jahjaga does not stand out in this aspect, although she had held a full constitutional mandate, in fact based on the above statistics she ranked behind her predecessors and successors in terms of decreeing the pardon of convicts. This is because for the same period that the current President Mr. Hashim Thaqi, who has decreed the pardon of fifty (50) convicts, is in power, the President had decreed only twenty-one (21) convicts.

In conclusion, it should be emphasized that the real challenge of the institutions of the Republic of Kosovo, specifically of the people who administer justice or manage the judicial power, is to stand firmly on democratic principles, preceded first and foremost by moral and human ones. While the challenge of political forces is to guard against temptation, to have good will and foresight, so as not to undermine the separation of powers and the independence of the judiciary (Panda, 2010, p. 91). As a result, the proper administration of justice by the President of the Republic of Kosovo results in positive consequences that consist in the guarantee of the rule of law in the state of Kosovo.

Conclusion

From the scientific research conducted regarding the relationship of the President of the Republic of Kosovo with the judiciary, we conclude that:

The state of Kosovo is a parliamentary republic based on the principle of separation of state powers and balanced control between them.

The justice system is considered an integral part of all constitutions and as such has a place in the Constitution of the Republic of Kosovo. A separate chapter of the constitution includes not only the judiciary, but also the Prosecution and the Bar.

The Constitution of the Republic of Kosovo should be amended to address the President's powers to refuse to appoint judges and prosecutors.

From the legal definition of the President's power to pardon convicted persons, it results that it is an executive power.

The exercise of the power to pardon convicted persons by the President affects the aspect of resocialization and re-education of convicted persons.

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